

Novus Scientia 2026

23. Medzinárodná vedecká konferencia doktorandov strojnícych fakúlt technických univerzít a vysokých škôl

Novus Scientia 2026

**Zborník príspevkov z XXIII. Medzinárodnej vedeckej konferencie doktorandov
strojnícych fakúlt technických univerzít a vysokých škôl**

29.01.2026

Strojnícka fakulta

Technická univerzita v Košiciach

Zameranie konferencie:

- Automatizácia, mechatronika a robotika
- Technologické a materiálové inžinierstvo
- Manažment, priemyselné a digitálne inžinierstvo
- Konštrukčné a procesné inžinierstvo
- Špeciálne inžinierske procesológie

Vedecký a organizačný výbor konferencie

Patronát konferencie

Dr.h.c. mult. prof. Ing. Jozef Živčák, DrSc., MPH, akademik UčSS

Technická univerzita v Košiciach, Slovensko

Garant konferencie

prof. Ing. Ján Slota, PhD.

Technická univerzita v Košiciach, Slovensko

Vedecký výbor konferencie

prof. Ing. Jozef Bocko, CSc., Technická univerzita v Košiciach, Slovensko

Dr.h.c. mult. prof. Ing. Miroslav Badida, PhD., Technická univerzita v Košiciach, Slovensko

prof. Ing. Michal Kelemen, PhD., Technická univerzita v Košiciach, Slovensko

prof. Ing. et Ing. Peter Trebuňa, PhD., Technická univerzita v Košiciach, Slovensko

prof. Ing. Emil Spišák, CSc., Technická univerzita v Košiciach, Slovensko

prof. Ing. Tomáš Brestovič, PhD., Technická univerzita v Košiciach, Slovensko

prof. Ing. Ján Král, PhD., Technická univerzita v Košiciach, Slovensko

prof. Ing. Peter Frankovský, PhD., Technická univerzita v Košiciach, Slovensko

prof. Ing. Marek Kočíško, PhD., Technická univerzita v Košiciach, Slovensko

prof. Ing. Michal Holubčík, PhD., Žilinská univerzita v Žiline, Slovensko

prof. Ing. Marcela Pokusová, PhD., Slovenská technická univerzita v Bratislave, Slovensko

prof. Ing. Peter Šugár, CSc., Slovenská technická univerzita v Bratislave, Slovensko

doc. Ing. Jaroslav Katolický, Ph.D., Vysoké učení technické Brno, Česká republika

doc. Ing. Miroslav Mahdal, Ph.D., VŠB Technická univerzita Ostrava, Česká republika

prof. Ing. Tomáš Jirout, Ph.D., ČVUT Praha, Česká republika

doc. Ing. Petr Lepšík, Ph.D., Technická univerzita v Liberci, Česká republika

doc. Ing. Václav Vaněk, Ph.D., Západočeská univerzita v Plzni, Česká republika

prof. dr. hab. inž. Andrzej Burghardt, Politechnika Rzeszowska, Poľsko

Dr inž. Tomasz Jachowicz, Politechnika Lubelska, Poľsko

Dr inž. Jacek Rysiński, Uniwersytet Bielsko – Bialski, Poľsko

Členovia odbornej komisie

prof. Ing. Jozef Kuľka, PhD.

doc. Ing. Miriam Pekarčíková, PhD.

prof. Ing. Miroslav Pástor, PhD.

prof. Ing. Michal Kelemen, PhD.

doc. Ing. Ludmila Dulebová, PhD.

doc. Ing. Teodor Tóth, PhD.

Organizačný výbor konferencie

prof. Ing. Ján Slota, PhD.

Ing. Jaroslav Melko

Ing. Erika Dubňanská

Ing. Martina Hančinová

Ing. Barbara Schürger

Ing. Veronika Sedláková

Ing. Katarína Dudová

Recenzovaný zborník z vedeckej konferencie

Príspevky v zborníku z vedeckej konferencie boli recenzované recenzentmi prostredníctvom anonymného recenzného konania.

Novus Scientia 2026

Zborník príspevkov z XXIII. Medzinárodnej vedeckej konferencie doktorandov strojnícckých fakúlt technických univerzít a vysokých škôl

- Názov:** Novus Scientia 2026
- Editor:** © prof. Ing. Ján Slota, PhD.
© Ing. Erika Dubňanská
© Ing. Martina Hančinová
© Ing. Barbara Schürger
- Vydavateľ:** Technická univerzita v Košiciach,
Strojnícka fakulta,
Letná 1/9, 042 00 Košice-Sever
- Rok:** 2026
- Náklad:** 75 výtlačkov
- Rozsah:** 374 strán
- Miesto konania:** Strojnícka fakulta, Technická univerzita v Košiciach
- Dátum konania:** 29.01.2026

ISBN 978-80-553-5042-4

OBSAH

Autorský kolektív a názov príspevku	Strany
ALI T., ŽIVČÁK J., ŠIŠKOVÁ S.: Biomechanical factors in the pathophysiology and clinical features of Wilkie syndrome	8 – 12
BADIDOVÁ M., SOBOTOVÁ L.: Research on non-exhaust ultrafine particles generated by car driving	13 – 20
BENDA M. M., SPIŠÁK E., MULIDRÁN P.: Experimental analysis of the influence of layer order in double-layer blanking of electrical steel sheets with variable strength properties	21 – 27
BÖSZÖRMÉNYI P., SCHNITZER M., HUDÁK R., ŽIVČÁK J., ŠEVČÍK T.: Patient-Specific Surgical Guide for Ulna Reconstruction Using CT-Based Digital Planning and Additive Manufacturing	28 – 33
BRADA L., MIKOVÁ L., PRADA E.: Design of educational tool for PID motor control	34 – 40
BRNA J., SUKOP M.: Design and Evaluation of a Cross-Platform Communication Architecture for Industrial Data Exchange	41 – 45
BUBER M., TOMÁŠ M.: Analysis of the cup-wall thickness change during deep drawing of a bearing housing	46 – 52
BUČKO M., DIŽO J., SAMAŠ V., SLUŠŇÁK P.: Design of a Double-Axle Bogie for Regional Rail Vehicles	53 – 58
CICHÝ M., DUPLÁKOVÁ D.: Current State and Potential Applications of Real-Time Data for Predictive Assessment of Ergonomic Risks in Industry	59 – 64
ČAJKOVÁ J., TREBUŇOVÁ M., BAČENKOVÁ D.: MSC Senescence in Prolonged Biocompatibility Evaluation of Biomaterials	65 – 70
ČURMA P., MILENOVSKÝ P., LÁZÁR M.: Development of an Apparatus for Recycling Metal Hydride Alloys	71 – 76
DIVOKOVÁ V., HUDÁK R., DIVOK M.: Application potential of physiologically beneficial vibrations in traumatological practice	77 – 83
DOMINIK F., SLOTA J., VRABEL M., KUŠNÍR J., PILÁT P.: Automation of VRFB component production using a custom-made vacuum fixture	84 – 89
DUBŇANSKÁ E., HANČINOVÁ M., SCHÜRGER B., HUŇADY R.: Numerical Modelling and Simulation of the Buildability of a 3D-Printed Component Using Grasshopper Plugin	90 – 94
DUDOVÁ K., BEDNARČÍKOVÁ L., ŽIVČÁK J.: Quantitative and Visual Assessment of Burn Scars Using 3D Scanning	95 – 100
DZURŇÁK P., MANTIČ M.: Image classification using convolutional neural network in container spreader control process	101 – 105
EIBEN V., KRÁLIKOVÁ R., LUMNITZER E.: Advancing Technical Research through Thermal Imaging: Educational Perspectives and Case Studies	106 – 114
GREGA M., BREZINOVÁ J.: Influence of chemical composition, inclusions and microcracks on the mechanical properties of G24Mn6 type steel	115 – 122
HANČINOVÁ M., DUBŇANSKÁ E., SCHÜRGER B., HUŇADY R., MACHALLA M.: Finite Element Simulation of Tensile Test of Silicone Material	123 – 129

<i>IVANECKÝ J., KULEKA J., VIROSTKO M.</i> : Analysis of accuracy of additive technology models	130 – 135
<i>KAPRAL V., GAJDOŠ I., KRASINSKYI V., LIOSIS CH.</i> : Analysis of the Hopper Shape in the Extruder Feeding Section	136 – 142
<i>KEREKEŠ S., SCHÜRGER B., DELYOVA I., FRANKOVSKÝ P.</i> : Kinematic Design and Functional Principle of a Kinetic Sculpture Mechanism	143 – 147
<i>KOKARDA V.</i> : Comparison of EDX and LIBS analytical methods in evaluating technical cleanliness in industrial applications	148 – 158
<i>KORDOŠOVÁ M., TÓTH T., BEDNARČÍKOVÁ L., MICHALÍKOVÁ M.</i> : Digitization of custom orthotic insole manufacturing	159 – 164
<i>KUŠNÍR J., DEMKO M., BRINDZA J., VRABEL M., DOMINIK F.</i> : Experimental data acquisition from a milling fixture	165 – 172
<i>LEŠČINSKÝ M., KOVÁČ J.</i> : Extension of an Open-Source Control System for Bimanual Robotic Manipulation Using CyberGlove Data Gloves	173 – 179
<i>LEVICKÁ S., PRAŽÁK D., SEDLÁK V., NAJMANOVÁ E., PLUHÁČEK F.</i> : International metrological comparison of ocular tonometers for optometry purposes	180 – 184
<i>MAJERČÁK O., ŠARGA P., RÁKAY R.</i> : Detection of compressed air leakage using compressor energy consumption analysis	185 – 191
<i>MALAKHOV D., KELEMENOVÁ T.</i> : Overview of calibration methods for measuring microscopes	192 – 199
<i>MÁLIK M., JÁNOŠ R.</i> : Communication Layer Compatibility in Cross-Generation ROS Systems	200 – 205
<i>MAŠLANKA M., PYTKA D., WALUSZEK M.</i> : Sound Generator Selection for Musical Tesla Coils	206 – 210
<i>MELKO J., JÁNOŠ R., MLINARČEK D., BRNA J.</i> : Methodology of Design and Simulation Verification of the Air Force TUKE Pneumatic Drive	211 – 216
<i>MINALE Y. F., GAJDOŠ I., SZABO T., POLYÁKNÉ KOVÁCS A., MAROSSY K., ÁDÁMNÉ MAJOR A.</i> : Segmental Dynamics and Thermo-Mechanical Response of PVC/TPU Blends Plasticized with a Bio-Based Plasticizer	217 – 221
<i>NOVOTNÝ Š., PALKO M.</i> : Design of engine modifications and construction for an experimental vehicle	222 – 227
<i>ONDERČO P., RYBÁŘ J., LEJA J., ĎURIŠ S.</i> : Construction of timetables in urban public transport from a metrological perspective	228 – 232
<i>PALOVÁ K., KELEMENOVÁ T.</i> : The Surface Roughness Standards	233 – 238
<i>PILÁT P., VARGA J., SEMJON J., DOMINIK F., TAKÁČ K.</i> : IMU-Based experimental verification of the stability of a specialized robotic locomotion system for pipeline environments	239 – 246
<i>PORUBČANOVÁ D., ZÁBAVSKÝ T., BALÁŽIKOVÁ M.</i> : Assessment of the impact of noise on mental stress	247 – 251
<i>ROMANČÍK J., VAGAŠ M., MAJERČÁK O.</i> : Integration of Shape-Memory Alloy Actuator into a Scissor-Mechanism Gripper Design	252 – 256
<i>RUDA F., SPIŠÁK E.</i> : Influence of Rolling Mill Parameters on the Mechanical and Surface Properties of Thin Galvanized Sheets	257 – 262

<i>RUSIŇÁK D., VIRGALA I.</i> : A Data-Driven Forward Kinematics Model for a Tendon-Driven Continuum Robot Using MLP-Based Regression	263 – 268
<i>SAMAŠ V., BUČKO M., GERLICI J., SLUŠŇÁK P.</i> : Design and Testing of a Device for Measuring Flywheel Brake Rotation to Enhance Static Friction Coefficient Evaluation	269 – 275
<i>SAVKOVÁ N., ŠTEFANOVIČ B., IVANČOVÁ E., SCHNITZER M., ŽIVČÁK J.</i> : Advancing Early Cleft Care: The Role of Intraoral Scanning (IOS) in Neonatal Patients – A Case Report and Literature Review	276 – 285
<i>SEDLÁKOVÁ V., HUDÁK R., TÓTH T., HAKULIN D.</i> : Overview of the Effects of Vibrations on Stem Cells	286 – 290
<i>SCHÜRGER B., FRANKOVSKÝ P., HANČINOVÁ M., DUBŇANSKÁ E., KEREKEŠ S.</i> : Metamaterials for Smart and Sustainable Cities	291 – 297
<i>STARINSKÝ G., RYBÁŘ J., ONDERČO P., BENČAT A., GERNESCHOVÁ J., SMETÁNKA A.</i> : The use of digital calibration certificates in healthcare	298 – 301
<i>SUKOPOVÁ D., FILO M., KÁDÁROVÁ J., LEŠČINSKÁ L.</i> : Trends in the Use of Artificial Intelligence in Enterprises in Slovakia and the EU and Their Relationship to Performance Indicators	302 – 304
<i>SZÁSZI D., KRÁE J.</i> : Use of simulation methods in production machines using virtual and augmented reality	305 – 310
<i>ŠIŠKA R., SLOTA J.</i> : Analysis of the Effect of Surface Treatment of Shearing Tools on the Accuracy and Quality of Roll-Bonded Sheet Cutting	311 – 315
<i>ŠIŠKOVÁ S., ŽIVČÁK J., ALI T., VINCZE L., DEÁKOVÁ D., ŠČIPÁKOVÁ M.</i> : Abdominopelvic Vascular Compression Syndromes: Pathophysiological Mechanisms and Connective Tissue Links	316 – 321
<i>ŠPURO P., CZAN A., SAJGALIK M., DRBUL M., MARKOVIC J., SCOTKA A.</i> : Effect of Laser Shock Peening on Additively Manufactured Components	322 – 327
<i>ŠTEFČÁK P., GAJDOŠ I., SOBASZEK Ł., MINALE Y. F.</i> : Definition and application of process tools for rib structure design in Large-scale additive manufacturing	328 – 332
<i>TOMKOVÁ V., SLOTA J.</i> : Manufacturing possibilities of steel sheets with organic coatings, their testing and damage in practice	333 – 340
<i>VARJÚ E., KOVÁČ J.</i> : Implementation of Realistic Physical Interactions for Maintenance Tools in Unity3D	341 – 348
<i>VILCHA J., FERKO J., ŽIVČÁK J.</i> : Follicular cyst removal and stabilization with 3D planned splint - case report	349 – 353
<i>VIROSTKO M., MANTIČ M., MALÁKOVÁ S., IVANECKÝ J.</i> : Generative Design for Spur Gear Optimization	354 – 358
<i>WALUSZEK M., MAŠLANKA M., PYTKA D.</i> : Real-Time Machine Vision Inspection of Embedded Inserts on a Belt Feeder	359 – 364
<i>YEROMINA M., DUPLÁK J., MIKULÁŠKO S.</i> : Assessment of the productivity of a robotic dental production cell design using simulation tool	365 – 371

Analysis of the Hopper Shape in the Extruder Feeding Section

Viliam Kapral^{1,*}, Ivan Gajdoš¹, Volodymyr Krasinskyi² and Christos Liosis³

¹ Slovakia, Technical University of Košice, Department of Technology, Materials and Computer Supported Production, Mäsiarska 74,040 01 Košice; viliam.kapral@tuke.sk; ivan.gajdos@tuke.sk

² Poland, Łukasiewicz Research Network – Institute of Polymer Materials, Marii Skłodowskiej-Curie 55, Toruń; volodymyr.krasinskyi@impib.lukasiewicz.gov.pl

³ Greece, University of Thessaly, Department of Civil Engineering, Pedion Areos, GR-38334, Volos; liosischristos@uniwa.gr

* Correspondence: viliam.kapral@tuke.sk

Abstract: The geometric configuration of the hoppers feeding section plays a crucial role in determining the flow efficiency of granular polymer composites in extrusion processes. This analysis focuses on the discharge behavior of polybutylene succinate (PBS) reinforced with carbon nanotubes (CNTs), and evaluates how inlet geometry influences material throughput. Two hopper designs with identical global dimensions but differing inlet shapes (oval and rectangular with a rounded edge) were examined through Discrete Element Method (DEM) simulations and validated by experimental measurements using three pellet sizes. Results consistently showed that smaller particles discharge faster and that the rectangular inlet achieved higher throughput and shorter discharge times under identical conditions. The flow remained stable across all configurations with no signs of clogging, highlighting the role of geometrical optimization in enhancing mass flow. The data used in this evaluation originate from work conducted within the framework of the PROMATAI project, which investigated processing performance under varying material and design parameters. These findings underscore the significance of simulation based design in developing efficient feeding systems for biodegradable polymer composites and provide a foundation for further applied research in extrusion technology.

Keywords: Polybutylene Succinate, Carbon Nanotubes, Hopper Design, Discrete Element Method

1. Introduction

Biodegradable polymers have become a key focus in materials engineering due to the environmental persistence of conventional plastics. Polybutylene succinate (PBS) is one of the most widely studied candidates because it combines mechanical strength, thermal stability, and full biodegradability. Its properties can be further improved through nanoscale reinforcement with carbon nanotubes (CNTs), which are among the most effective additives. Even low CNT loadings significantly modify the crystallinity and structural behavior of PBS resulting in enhanced mechanical and thermal performance. CNT reinforced PBS composites therefore represent a promising class of materials for applications that require improved functional properties. [1] Since the processing behaviour of PBS/CNT composites strongly depends on the efficiency of granular feeding, an appropriate hopper design becomes essential for ensuring stable throughput during extrusion.

The flow behaviour of granular materials in hoppers is of great interest to many industries that involve the handling of bulk materials. The scale of hoppers varies from millilitres to thousands of litres depending on the desired hopper capacity, and the handled materials may range from cohesive particles to free flow particles. [2] Although most hoppers are simple in geometric configurations, the discharge flow dynamics can be complicated due to the influence of various factors related to the geometry of the hopper and the

characteristics of the flow media. Hopper design is critical because inappropriate design can result in poor operation performance and even equipment or functionality issues. [3] Since the flow characteristics of the granular material is of vital importance for the operational stability and structural integrity of these units, a deeper knowledge and understanding of the mechanical behavior within a hopper is necessary for the best possible design and operation. Nevertheless, a general approach for designing a hopper is not available. [4]

Particle discharge is one of the key physical processes governing the macroscopic flow behavior in hoppers. Factors affecting the discharge rate include hopper geometry and particle properties such as friction coefficient, shape, and size. [5] The Discrete Element Method (DEM) simulates the movement of granular materials by calculating the motion of individual particles based on Newton's second law, considering only contact interactions between neighboring particles. The resulting linear and rotational motions are determined by the summation of forces and moments acting at each contact. [6] Recent DEM studies have shown that particle flow behavior is strongly influenced by local arching, stress redistribution, and contact force chains within the granular assembly. These works demonstrate that DEM can accurately capture microstructural mechanisms, enabling detailed predictions of discharge rates and flow patterns across different hopper configurations. Furthermore, small variations in particle or wall properties can significantly affect clogging probability and mass flow discharge. [7] Predicting granular flow, however, remains challenging due to the strong coupling between particle–particle and particle–wall interactions. The discharge behavior is highly sensitive to parameters such as friction, particle shape, and surface roughness, as well as to local stress conditions. Even small changes in these factors can lead to marked differences in flow regimes, stress propagation, and overall discharge behavior. [8] To ensure the credibility of the numerical findings the simulated discharge behavior must be verified through controlled experimental measurements allowing a direct assessment of the agreement between modeled and real systems. Therefore, the objective of this study is to analyse how two hopper inlet geometries affect the discharge rate and flow stability of PBS/CNT pellets. The evaluation combines DEM simulations with experimental validation to identify geometric features that enhance feeding efficiency in extrusion processes.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Material Definitions for Hopper Feeding Analysis

Materials used in this study included the PBS/CNT composite prepared for testing, which served as the base material for evaluating the different hopper geometries. The polymer matrix consisted of polybutylene succinate (PBS) supplied by PTT MCC Biochem Company Limited (Bangkok, Thailand) under the trade name BioPBS™ FZ91PM. The nanofiller consisted of multi walled carbon nanotubes (CNT) supplied by Nanografi Nanotechnology (Ankara, Turkey) under the product code NG01IM0101 used at a concentration of 0.5 wt%. Higher CNT loadings were not considered as they typically increase melt viscosity and promote agglomeration, which complicates processing and reduces the functional performance of the composite. The PBS/CNT composite was prepared by melt compounding using a corotating twinscrew extruder BTKS 20/40D (Bühler, Germany). The extruded composite material was pelletized using a TS-40 pelletizer to produce pellets of 2×3 mm, 3×3 mm, and 5×3 mm. The measured PBS/CNT parameters are reported in Table 1. These pellet sizes were subsequently used in the DEM simulations and in the experimental measurements.

Table 1. Mechanical properties of PBS/CNT 0.5 wt % material.

Properties	Value
Density [g/cm ³]	1.27
Melting Point [°C]	114
Tensile Modulus [MPa]	575 – 620
Stress at Break [MPa]	30 – 32
Strain at Break [%]	125 – 208
Surface Tension [mN/m]	52

2.2. Geometry of the Hopper Feeding Section

Both CAD designed hopper variants were developed with identical global dimensions to enable a controlled comparison of their flow performance. Each hopper has a total height of 450 mm, an inlet width equal to the screw diameter of 45 mm and a wall inclination angle of 70°. Keeping these geometric parameters constant ensures that any differences observed in the material discharge behaviour can be attributed solely to the geometry of the feeding opening.

The variants differ exclusively in the shape of the inlet region, which defines the local geometry of the hopper walls. In the first design, shown in Figure 1a, the feeding opening has an oval profile with a length of 67.5 mm, corresponding to 1.5 times the inlet width, and an effective area of 3046 mm². In the second design, illustrated in Figure 1b, the opening is rectangular with one rounded shorter edge. The opening length remains identical at 67.5 mm, while the total area is larger, reaching 3355 mm². These two geometries were selected to examine how the cross sectional shape of the feeding opening influences the overall discharge characteristics under otherwise identical hopper conditions.

Figure 1. Top view CAD models of the two hopper variants (a) hopper with an oval shape, (b) hopper with a rectangular shape featuring one rounded shorter edge.

2.3. Discrete Element Method Simulation of Hopper Geometries

For each hopper variant three separate simulations were performed differing in the radius of the spherical particles $r_1 = 0.002414$ m, $r_2 = 0.001717$ m, and $r_3 = 0.001311$ m. These values do not represent the actual dimensions of the pellets (5×3 mm, 3×3 mm, and 2×3 mm), but their spherical equivalents. Since the DEM model operates with spherical particles it was necessary to transform the irregular shape of the pellets into a spherical form with a comparable volume. This approximation ensured the numerical stability of the model and enabled consistent comparison of the individual variants. The geometry of the

hoppers was divided into three parts: the filling plane through which the hopper was filled (the upper inlet), the hopper body, and the measuring plane, which closed the geometry during filling to prevent free particle discharge. At the moment the simulation was started the measuring plane served as a detection plane determining the number of discharged particles and the time required to empty the entire hopper volume. The remaining parameters used in the simulation are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Parameters used in the DEM simulation

Parameter	Value
Poisson's ratio	0.46
Rolling friction coefficient	0.8
Coefficient of restitution	0.5
Filling time [s]	4
Input mass rate [kg/s]	4
Gravity [$m \cdot s^{-2}$]	9.81
Iteration step [s]	10^{-5}

In the first hopper variant with an oval inlet, the filling with pellets lasted 4 s. After the hopper was filled, the particle exit phase began, which for all particle sizes r_1 , r_2 , and r_3 lasted between 4 and 7.75 s. After a short initial fluctuation, the flow stabilized and remained practically constant until the hopper was completely emptied. The particles with the largest radius r_1 required the most time to empty the entire hopper volume through the measuring plane namely 3.75 s with a total of 53 875 particles passing through the measuring plane. For particles with radius r_2 the exit time was 3.50 s and the number of particles was 149 717. The hopper volume was emptied the fastest by the particles with radius r_3 , in 3.35 s, with a total of 336 348 particles. Figure 2 provides a graphical representation of the discharge behavior for the hopper with an oval inlet, showing both the number particle count passing measuring plane and the particle flow rate for all three pellet radii.

Figure 2. Particle discharge characteristics (a) Total number of particles passing through the measuring plane for the hopper with oval inlet, (b) Number of particle rate for the hopper with a oval inlet.

For the second hopper configuration, the inlet was rectangular with one rounded shorter edge, the initial filling of the hopper volume proceeded similarly to the first variant however the geometry allowed more particles to be inserted into the hopper. The interval for emptying the hopper volume ranged from 4 to 7.5 s, which was the time required to empty 4 kg of material. For particles with radius r_1 the exit time was 3.50 s and the number of particles passing through the measuring plane was 53 924. The exit time for 149 653 particles with radius r_2 was 3.20 s. As in the first variant, the smallest particles

with radius r_3 required the shortest time to exit the hopper, namely 3.05 s, and the number of particles leaving the hopper volume was 336 015. Figure 3 illustrates the discharge behaviour for the hopper with a rectangular inlet with one rounded shorter edge, again showing the number particle count passing measuring plane and the particle flow rate.

Figure 3. Particle discharge characteristics (a) Total number of particles passing through the measuring plane for the hopper with a rectangular shape featuring one rounded shorter edge, (b) Number of particle rate for the hopper with a rectangular shape featuring one rounded shorter edge.

A comparison of the two simulated variants shows that the dominant factor influencing the emptying process is the particle size, as also reflected in Table 3, which clearly illustrates the progressively shorter discharge times for smaller radii. Smaller radii consistently led to a faster exit from the hopper volume and a higher number of particles passing through the measuring plane. The difference between the geometries manifested mainly in the amount of material that could be inserted into the hopper. The second geometry allowed for a larger number of particles to be loaded, while still maintaining a stable flow behaviour for all examined radii.

Table 3. Exit time for two inlet geometries at three pellet sizes [s].

Inlet geometry	Exit time at r_1	Exit time at r_2	Exit time at r_3
Oval inlet	3.75	3.50	3.35
Rectangular inlet (rounded edge)	3.50	3.20	3.05

2.4. Experimental Comparison of Hopper Geometries

For the purposes of the experiment, it was necessary to print prototype hoppers, which were manufactured on a Fortus 400mc 3D printer. Due to the limited size of the printing area, it was necessary to change the original hopper height from 450 mm to 350 mm. After printing the individual models, it was necessary to adjust the internal surfaces of the hoppers by sanding to ensure identical surface roughness ($R_a \approx 0.2 \mu\text{m}$) for both variants. Subsequently, a supporting structure was produced onto which the individual hoppers were mounted in order to minimize measurement deviation during the experiments. The opening and closing of the hopper were carried out using a pneumatic piston, which ensured a reproducible opening and closing speed throughout all tests. The throughput of both hopper variants was measured for all tested pellet sizes (2×3 mm, 3×3 mm, and 5×3 mm). For each combination, the experiment was repeated 10 times, resulting in a total of 60 measurements. The measurements were conducted in the laboratory of the Institute of Polymeric Materials (Instytut Materiałów Polimerowych, Poland).

The results of the experiment presented in Table 4 show that the hopper with the rectangular inlet featuring a rounded shorter edge achieves higher throughput than the hopper with the oval inlet, and this applies to all tested pellet sizes. For the 2×3 mm pellets,

an increase in throughput of 525 kg/h was recorded, corresponding to 13.3%. For the 3×3 mm pellets, the difference was 487 kg/h, i.e., 13.4%. The most pronounced effect was observed for the largest pellets, 5×3 mm, where the throughput increased by 620 kg/h, which corresponds to 16.2%. These results confirm that the enlarged area and modified shape of the discharge opening reduce the flow resistance of the granulate and enable a higher mass flow under identical boundary conditions.

Table 4. Measured throughput capacity for different inlet geometries [kg/h].

Pellet size [mm]	Oval inlet	Rectangular inlet (rounded edge)
2×3	3948	4473
3×3	3633	4120
5×3	3830	4450

Note: All values were measured with an uncertainty of ± 25 .

Table 5 summarizes the average discharge time of the material for the individual combinations of outlet geometry and pellet size. In all cases, a shorter discharge time was achieved with the rectangular outlet with a rounded shorter edge, which is consistent with the higher throughput presented in Table 4. For pellets of 2×2 mm, the discharge time was shorter by 0.43 s, which represents a 13.35% difference compared to the oval outlet. For the 3×3 mm size, the difference was 0.41 s, corresponding to 11.55%. The largest difference was observed for the 5×3 mm pellets, where the discharge time was shorter by 0.51 s, which corresponds to a 15.74% difference. The experimental results indicate that an appropriate modification of the outlet shape can significantly reduce the hopper discharge time without a negative impact on flow stability.

Table 5. Discharge time for two inlet geometries for three pellet sizes [s].

Pellet size [mm]	Oval inlet	Rectangular inlet (rounded edge)
2×3	3.65	3.22
3×3	3.96	3.55
5×3	3.75	3.24

3. Discussion

A comparison of the DEM simulation results with the experimental measurements shows a consistent trend in the discharge behaviour of pelletized material for both inlet geometries as summarized in Table 6. In all evaluated cases, the discharge time increased with increasing pellet size, which was captured in the simulation as well as in the experiment.

For the oval inlet, the DEM simulation consistently predicted shorter discharge times than the experiment. The deviations were 0.30 s for 2×3 mm pellets (3.35 s vs. 3.65 s), 0.46 s for 3×3 mm pellets (3.50 s vs. 3.96 s), and 0.00 s for 5×3 mm pellets (3.75 s vs. 3.75 s). Despite this offset, the model correctly reproduced the relative differences among pellet sizes. For the rectangular inlet with a rounded edge, the agreement was significantly better for the 2×3 mm pellets. The differences between simulation and experiment were smaller 0.17 s for pellets (3.05 s vs. 3.22 s), 0.35 s for 3×3 mm pellets (3.20 s vs. 3.55 s), and 0.26 s for 5×3 mm pellets (3.50 s vs. 3.24 s). These results indicate that the DEM model captured the discharge behaviour more accurately in this geometry, likely due to the more uniform outflow enabled by the enlarged effective opening.

Overall, the comparison confirms that the DEM simulation reliably reproduces the qualitative behavior of the pellet discharge process and provides quantitatively acceptable predictions. The model demonstrated sufficient accuracy to distinguish the influence of

pellet size and inlet geometry on discharge time. The rectangular inlet consistently enabled faster discharge in both the simulation and the experimental setup, which validates its suitability for applications requiring higher material throughput.

Table 6. Discharge time comparison between DEM simulation and experiment [s].

Pellet size [mm]	Oval inlet		Rectangular inlet (rounded edge)	
	Simulation time	Experiment time	Simulation time	Experiment time
2×3	3.35	3.65	3.05	3.22
3×3	3.50	3.96	3.20	3.55
5×3	3.75	3.75	3.50	3.24

Acknowledgments: This research was funded by the European Union's programme for research and innovation Horizon Europe under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Action grant agreement No 101129698-PROMATAI- Horizon-MSCA-2022-SE-01. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

References

1. MODYFIKACJA POLIMERÓW STAN I PERSPEKTYWY W ROKU 2025, MWCNT-Reinforced Biopbs for Sustainable Application, Krasinskyi, V., Bajer, K., Krasinska, O., Sarris, I., Dulebová, L., Ganusauskaitė, A., Mandula, D., TEMPO s.c., Wrocław, 2025, pp. 92-94, ISBN 978-83-86520-27-5
2. Jihoe, K., Dong-Woo, R., Investigation of discharge characteristics of rod-shaped particles in a hopper: Experimental and numerical studies using polygonal/polyhedral DEM, *Advanced Powder Technology*, Elsevier B.V., 2020, Volume 31, pp. 4207-4221, ISSN 0921-8831
3. Lai, Z., Xia, Y., Chen, Q., Discrete element modeling of granular hopper flow of irregular-shaped deformable particles, *Advanced Powder Technology*, Elsevier B.V., 2023, Volume 34, ISSN 0921-8831
4. Höhner, D., Wirtz, S., Scherer, V., A numerical study on the influence of particle shape on hopper discharge within the polyhedral and multi-sphere discrete element method, *Powder Technology*, Elsevier B.V., 2012, Volume 226, pp. 16-28, ISSN 0032-5910
5. Fan, J., Wang, H., Luu, L., Philippe, P., Wang, L., Wei, Z., Yu, J., Numerical study of granular discharge flows through centred and off-centred rectangular hoppers using discrete element simulations, *Powder Technology*, Elsevier B.V., 2023, Volume 429, ISSN 0032-5910
6. K. Tanaka, M. Nishida, T. Kunimochi, T. Takagi, Numerical and experimental studies for the impact of projectiles on granular materials, *Handbook of Powder Technology*, 1st ed, A. Levy, H. Kalman, Elsevier Science, Amsterdam, New York, 2001, Volume 10, pp. 263-270, ISBN 9780444502353
7. R. Balevičius, R. Kačianauskas, Z. Mróz, I. Sielamowicz, Analysis and DEM simulation of granular material flow patterns in hopper models of different shapes, *Advanced Powder Technology*, Elsevier B.V., 2011, Volume 22, pp. 226-235, ISSN 0921-8831
8. Bovo, E., Sorgato, M., Lucchetta, G., An image-based approach for the mass flow measurement of plastic granules as an alternative solution to loss-in-weight feeding systems, *Powder Technology*, Elsevier B.V., 2023, Volume 430, ISSN 0032-5910

Novus Scientia 2026

Zborník príspevkov z XXIII. Medzinárodnej vedeckej konferencie doktorandov
strojnícckých fakúlt technických univerzít a vysokých škôl

- Názov:** Novus Scientia 2026
- Editor:** © prof. Ing. Ján Slotá, PhD.
© Ing. Erika Dubňanská
© Ing. Martina Hančinová
© Ing. Barbara Schürger
- Vydavateľ:** Technická univerzita v Košiciach,
Strojnícka fakulta,
Letná 1/9, 042 00 Košice-Sever
- Rok:** 2026
- Náklad:** 75 výtlačkov
- Rozsah:** 374 strán
- Miesto konania:** Strojnícka fakulta, Technická univerzita v Košiciach
- Dátum konania:** 29.01.2026

ISBN 978-80-553-5042-4